

Resistance to rice whorl maggot (RWM) and leaffolder (LF) in the north-central plateau of Orissa, India

H. P. Patnaik, Regional Research Station (RRS), Keonjhar 758002, Orissa; N. C. Patnaik, Entomology Department, Orissa University of Agriculture and Technology, Bhubaneswar 751003; and K.M. Samal, R. R.S., Keonjhar, Orissa, India

Rice mite *Oligonychus oryzae* (Hirst) incidence on IR elite lines

P. Karuppuchamy, R. Velusamy, R. Rajendran, and P. C. Sundara Bahu, Agricultural Entomology Department, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore 641003, India

Thirteen IR elite lines and 6 rice varieties were transplanted in 3 rows of 2 m each in the screenhouse. A severe incidence of rice mite 50 d after planting caused leaf yellowing. Mite populations were recorded in 1-cm² area/leaf on 10 leaves taken at random from 10 hills/elite line.

IR35546-52-3-3-2 had fewer mites, followed by IR29723-143-3-2-1, IR5, IR25587-133-3-2-2-2, IR50, and IR64 (see table). Mite populations were high on ADT36 and TN1. □

Rice mite *O. oryzae* populations on IR elite lines at Coimbatore, India.

Variety or breeding line	Mites ^a (no.)/10 cm ²
IR35546-52-3-3-2	17.5 a
IR29723-143-3-2-1	32.0 b
IR5	33.0 b
IR25587-133-3-2-2-2	38.0 bc
IR50	38.5 bcd
IR64	38.5 bcd
IR25588-7-3-1	44.5 cde
IR29723-88-2-3-3	45.0 cde
IR32808-54-3-1-39	47.0 cdef
IR28222-9-2-2-2-2	48.0 defg
IR29692-65-2-3-3	49.5 efgh
IR32429-47-3-2-2	52.0 efgh
IR31802-48-2-2-2	52.5 efgh
IR331868-64-2-3-3-3	53.0 efgh
IR62	56.0 fgh
IR29725-109-1-2-1	56.0 fgh
IR28150-84-3-3-2	57.0 gh
TN1	59.0 h
ADT36	67.0 i

^aMean of 2 replications. Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 0.05% level by DMRT.

We studied the reaction of 22 medium-duration (101-125 d) and 24 medium-late-duration (126-140 d) rice cultivars to RWM and LF in the 1986 wet season. Plant populations were 450/cultivar at 15 × 10 cm spacing. RWM leaf count was recorded at 30 d

after transplanting (DT) and LF incidence at 50 DT on random samples of 10 plants.

No entry was free of RWM and LF infestation (see table). Most exhibited moderate resistance. □

Reaction of rice cultivars to RWM and LF in Orissa, India.

Entry	Cross	Leaf infestation (%)	
		RWM 30 DT	LF 50 DT
<i>Medium duration (101-125 d)</i>			
ORI31-5-8	Kumar/CR57-49	19.3	16.0
OR131-8-5	Kumar/CR57-49	16.0	18.7
OR135-3-4	OR10-26/CR57-49	17.3	16.0
OR158-7-1	IR8/Siam 29//Parijat	26.7	20.0
OR194-1	Adt 27/IR8//Parijat	13.3	13.3
OR367-B-1	IR7687 (Mahsuri/IR30)	17.3	8.0
OR372-B-13	IR9093 (73-1196-12/IR30//IR2071-625-1)	34.7	34.7
OR375-SP-36	IR10904 (IR30/ARC5929)	13.3	16.0
OR378-1	IR11201 (IR2070-414-3-9-6/Mahsuri)	12.0	26.7
OR409-5	IR30/Suphala	20.0	9.3
OR4 10-7	IR28/Suphala//OR78-19	10.7	16.0
OR495-7	Annapurna/IET1444	37.3	24.0
OR556-37	Parijat/Annapurna	8.0	37.3
ORS26-2016-10-1	Obs 677/IR2071//RPb-13/W1263	10.7	5.3
Annapurna	Ptb 10/TN1	5.3	18.7
Daya	Kumar/CR57-49	6.7	17.3
IR36	IR8/Tadukan//TKM 6/TN1///IR24/ <i>O. nivara</i>	5.3	16.0
Keshari	Kumar/Jagannath	16.0	36.0
Pusa 2-21	IR8/TKM6	13.3	13.3
Sarathi	OR10-135/W1263	8.0	29.3
Nayagarh-Kanhei	Local check	5.3	12.0
Sri Rama-Kashipur	Local check	8.0	9.3
<i>Medium-late duration (126-140 d)</i>			
OR42-10	BAM-6/IR8	6.7	18.7
OR290-4-4	Jagannath/Dular	12.0	22.7
OR297-10-1	Rajeswari/T141//IET1444	12.0	26.7
OR310-2-2	Hema/CR57//RPb-13/Sakti//ORS952	8.0	21.3
OR297-10-2	Rajeswari/T141//IET1444	12.0	14.7
OR364-B-3	IR7137 (73-1095/IR2070-747-6)	16.0	14.7
OR364-SP-19	IR7137 (73-1095/IR2070-747-6)	2.7	16.0
OR367-SP-42	IR7687 (Mahsuri/IR30)	10.7	17.3
OR369-IB-10	IR8422 (BG 34-8/IR2070-414-3-9-6)	5.3	24.0
OR370-B-4	IR8703 (IR32/Mahsuri)	22.7	16.0
OR371-SP-12	IR8918 (Obs 677/IR2070-423-2-57)	17.3	16.0
OR372-B-11	IR9093 (73-1196-12/IR30//IR2071-625-1)	9.3	20.0
OR372-B-20	IR9093 (73-1196-12/IR30//IR2071-625-1)	6.7	21.3
OR373-IB-4-1	IR9264 (Mahsuri/IR2061-213-2-16//IR2061-213-2-16)	8.0	12.0
OR380-B-12	IR11602 (Ratna/IR2071-625-1-252)	2.7	12.0
OR405-4	Dular (Dwarf)/T1145//Dular (Dwarf)	6.7	22.7
OR409-31	IR30/Suphala	9.3	10.7
ORS26-2008-4	Obs 677/IR2071//RPb-13/W1263	16.0	16.0
ORS26-2014-4	Obs 677/IR2071//RPb-13/W1263	10.7	28.0
Jajati	Rajeswari/T141	18.7	20.0
Pratap	Kumar/CR57-49	9.3	24.0
Kaincha	Local check	8.0	8.0
Sarubhojani	Local check	6.7	14.7
Suryakanti	Local check	4.0	13.3